

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	Gabi Project
				Min: 62.403 Max: 62.590	1446 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1433-4 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION
compact layer below 1424

Covered by SU: 1424 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

SOIL/MATRIX
clay 5% silt 75% sand 20%
 Granular Layered Cohesive

Compaction	Color
<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Depth: Original Not Original
*original above bedrock
not original above fill 1432*

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: _____ Is bound to (only for masonry): _____

Is abutted by: _____ Abuts: _____

Is covered by: 1424 Covers: 1001

Is cut by: _____ Cuts: _____

Is filled by: _____ Fills: 1431

OBSERVATIONS
very compact material. western portion has smooth compaction while eastern portion has small rock inclusions

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: *South central of area B 2011, north of SU1429 and southwest of SU1424*
 Shape: *irregular*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): *downward, southeast, small rocks in eastern portion; two large stones in southwest*

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): *cluster of stone in southwest*

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): _____

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight
 Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping
 Cut bottom: flat concave irregular
 How is cut top edge? sharp rounded
 How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded
 Observations: _____

Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Accumulation layer extending from northwestern corner of cut 1431 northward. Area may have been excavated by previous excavator. Region of SW to north and east were found to be bedrock.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by Z. Fox

on 7/26/11

Revised by CMH

on 20.7.11

PDFd by ECR

on 27-7-11

Entered by

on